

MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES WITH PORES

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a procedure to model carbon/carbon composites containing pores of irregular shapes. Closed form expressions for contributions of fibres and pores into effective elastic moduli are provided. The procedure is applied to predict the transverse elastic properties of unidirectional carbon / carbon composites (carbon fibres in pyrolytic carbon matrix) densified by chemical vapor infiltration. Infiltration treatment results in formation of irregularly shaped pores randomly oriented in the plane perpendicular to the direction of fibre (transverse plane). These pores are analyzed using numerical conformal mapping technique, and their contribution to the effective elastic properties is expressed in terms of the cavity compliance contribution tensor. Components of this tensor are found for a variety of typical pore shapes.

KEYWORDS: carbon/carbon composites, irregularly shaped pores, micromechanics.

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a micromechanical procedure to model fibre reinforced composites containing pores of irregular shapes. The procedure is applied to predict the effective elastic moduli of unidirectional carbon/carbon composites (C/C) fabricated by chemical vapour infiltration (CVI) of carbon fibre pre-form. The technology of chemical vapour infiltration consists of synthesis of pyrolytic carbon (Pyro-C) particles from hydrocarbon gas (methane/hydrogen mixture) and their deposition on carbon fibres preliminarily placed in that environment. The process runs under the temperature of up to 1100°C and total pressures of 20 to 30 kPa until the carbon particles deposit and form a porous carbon matrix filling the space between the fibres. Pores in this matrix have highly irregular shapes as shown in Fig. 1. Further details on the infiltration procedure and sample properties are given in [1].

Micromechanical modelling of porous C/C composite presents several challenges. First, constituents in the composite have different length scales: the diameter of fibres used in such composites is on the order of 10 µm while some pores reach up to hundreds of microns in dimensions. Secondly, pores are of irregular shapes, and cannot be easily analysed by regular elasticity solutions. And finally, the open porosity in these composites is much smaller than the total porosity, thus the latter must be determined by microscopic analysis.

Fig. 1: Typical microstructure of CVI densified C/C composite

To model composite material having constituents of different length scale, we employ a two-step homogenization procedure described in [2], see Fig. 2. First, the contribution of fibres is accounted for by substituting Pyro-C matrix and carbon fibres with an equivalent matrix material (denoted by a subscript FPC). Then, the irregular pores (now embedded in the homogenized matrix FPC) are analyzed using a numerical conformal mapping technique [3]. The quantification of the microstructure is performed through the digital analysis of the micrographs as described in the next section.

Fig. 2: Two-step micromechanical modelling procedure of porous C/C composite

MICROSTRUCTURE OF THE COMPOSITE

For the detailed analysis, we have chosen a specimen of the unidirectional carbon/carbon composite manufactured using the procedure described in Introduction. Typical micrographs, obtained by optical light microscopy [4], are shown in Fig. 3a. We observe the bright circular regions representing fibres surrounded by the Pyro-C matrix, while large black regions of irregular shape indicate pores (cavities). The diameter of fibres is $7 \mu\text{m}$, and the typical pore dimensions are on the order of tens of microns.

The micrographic images of the composite were processed and digitally analyzed using ColorPoint 2.0 software (www.patrilab.com). Fig. 3b shows examples of processed data. Images presented in Fig. 3 and thirteen other 200 μm and 500 μm scale images have been analyzed to obtain fibre volume fraction V_f , Pyro-C volume fraction V_{PC} and porosity V_p of the composite. The resulting estimates are: $V_f = 18\%$, $V_p = 29\%$, $V_{PC} = 53\%$. These values are used in the subsequent analysis.

Fig. 3: Microstructure of CVI densified C/C composite on a 500 μm length scale.

(a) typical microstructure images

(b) processed images: Gray - pores, Black - fibres and Pyro-C

As can be seen in Figs. 1 and 3, pores in this composite material are randomly distributed in the transverse plane without any preferential orientation. Their shapes are highly irregular and cannot be accurately approximated by circles, ellipses or right polygons for which the analytical elasticity solutions are available. It is also observed that the location of the fibres in the transverse plane is random, so the overall elastic properties of the composite are transversely isotropic. To analyze the transverse elastic moduli of such a composite, we employ the near-field micromechanical modeling procedure, which is based on the concept of the compliance contribution tensor as described in [5, 6]. It is assumed that pores are sufficiently long in the direction of fibre, so that the plane strain model can be used. Also, the pyrolytic carbon matrix material, which can be high-textured and anisotropic on the nano-scale, is modeled as homogeneous and isotropic on the length scale of fibres and pores.

TWO-STEP MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING PROCEDURE

Contribution of Fibres

Micromechanical modelling of the linear elastic material reinforced by unidirectional fibres of circular cross-section is based on the plane strain elasticity solution for a circular inclusion in the infinite two-dimensional solid. According to Hardiman [7], the stress in such inclusion subjected to remotely applied uniaxial tension P is uniform:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_f = P(c_1 \mathbf{e}_1 \otimes \mathbf{e}_1 + c_2 \mathbf{e}_2 \otimes \mathbf{e}_2) \quad (1)$$

where $c_1 = \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{1 + \beta + \gamma}{\beta - \gamma(1 - 2\beta + 2\gamma)}$, $c_2 = -\frac{\beta}{2} \frac{1 - \beta + 3\gamma}{\beta - \gamma(1 - 2\beta + 2\gamma)}$, $\beta = \frac{E_f}{E_{PC}} \frac{1 - \nu_{PC}^2}{1 - \nu_f^2}$, and

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\beta}{1 - \nu_{PC}} - \frac{1}{1 - \nu_f} \right).$$

In Eqn. 1, the transverse elastic properties of fibres and Pyro-C material have been assumed isotropic with Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios E_f , ν_f and E_{PC} , ν_{PC} , correspondingly. Boldface letters are used to denote vectors and tensors. Following the homogenisation procedure developed in [2], we represent the elastic compliance of the carbon fibre reinforced matrix as a sum of two terms:

$$\mathbf{S}^{(FPC)} = \mathbf{S}^{(PC)} + \mathbf{H}^{(f)} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{S}^{(PC)}$ is the average compliance of the pyrolytic carbon, and $\mathbf{H}^{(f)}$ is the fibres' compliance contribution tensor. The components of this tensor can be calculated using the Mori-Tanaka micromechanical model (see [6]) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{1111}^{(f)} = H_{2222}^{(f)} &= V_f \left[\frac{d_1(c_1 + c_2)}{1 - V_f(1 - c_1 - c_2)} + \frac{d_2(c_1 - c_2)}{1 - V_f(1 - c_1 + c_2)} \right] \\ H_{1122}^{(f)} = H_{2211}^{(f)} &= V_f \left[\frac{d_1(c_1 + c_2)}{1 - V_f(1 - c_1 - c_2)} - \frac{d_2(c_1 - c_2)}{1 - V_f(1 - c_1 + c_2)} \right] \\ H_{1212}^{(f)} = H_{2121}^{(f)} = H_{1221}^{(f)} = H_{2112}^{(f)} &= V_f \frac{d_2(c_1 - c_2)}{1 - V_f(1 - c_1 + c_2)} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $d_1 = \frac{(1 - \nu_f - 2\nu_f^2)E_{PC} - (1 - \nu_{PC} - 2\nu_{PC}^2)E_f}{2E_{PC}E_f}$ and $d_2 = \frac{(1 + \nu_f)E_{PC} - (1 + \nu_{PC})E_f}{2E_{PC}E_f}$. The

Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the homogenized carbon fibre / pyrolytic carbon mixture are

$$E_{FPC} = \frac{A_1 - 2A_2}{(-A_1 + A_2)^2}, \quad \nu_{FPC} = \frac{A_2}{-A_1 + A_2} \quad (4)$$

where coefficients A_1 and A_2 are expressed as

$$A_1 = \frac{1 - \nu_{PC}^2}{E_{PC}} + \frac{V_f d_1 (c_1 + c_2)}{1 - V_f (1 - c_1 - c_2)} + \frac{V_f d_2 (c_1 - c_2)}{1 - V_f (1 - c_1 + c_2)},$$

$$A_2 = -\frac{\nu_{PC} + \nu_{PC}^2}{E_{PC}} + \frac{V_f d_1 (c_1 + c_2)}{1 - V_f (1 - c_1 - c_2)} - \frac{V_f d_2 (c_1 - c_2)}{1 - V_f (1 - c_1 + c_2)}.$$

Contribution of Pores

The effective elastic properties of the entire composite also include the contribution of the irregularly shaped pores: $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S}^{(FPC)} + \mathbf{H}^{(p)}$. This results in the following expressions for the overall transverse Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio

$$E = \frac{E_{FPC}}{1 + \sum_N V_p^{(N)} \left(\frac{3}{8} (h_1 + h_2) + \frac{1}{4} (h_3 + h_4) \right)_N}, \quad \nu = \frac{\nu_{FPC} - \sum_N p_N \left(\frac{1}{8} (h_1 + h_2) + \frac{3}{4} h_4 - \frac{1}{4} h_3 \right)_N}{1 + \sum_N V_p^{(N)} \left(\frac{3}{8} (h_1 + h_2) + \frac{1}{4} (h_3 + h_4) \right)_N}$$

where $(h_1 \dots h_4)_N$ and $V_p^{(N)}$ are the shape factors and porosity of the pores of N -th type. The numerical conformal mapping procedure to calculate the shape factors of irregularly shaped holes is given in [3]. The results for some typical Pyro-C pore shapes are presented in Table 1.

As can be seen from Table 1, the numerical values of h -coefficients vary greatly for different pore shapes - they depend not only on the pore shape but also on its orientation with respect to coordinate axes. However, for sufficiently large number of pores of each shape randomly distributed and oriented in the material, only two combinations of these coefficients describe contribution of each defect shape:

$$A = \frac{3}{8} (h_1 + h_2) + \frac{1}{4} (h_3 + h_4), \quad B = \frac{1}{8} (h_1 + h_2) + \frac{3}{4} h_4 - \frac{1}{4} h_3 \quad (5)$$

The analysis of calculated values of A and B for each shape (Table 1) shows surprising closeness of these parameters for different geometries of pores present in Pyro-C. We attribute this fact to the identical manufacturing process during which they were formed.

Thus, the effective transverse elastic moduli of the unidirectional porous CVI densified C/C composite are

$$E = \frac{E_{FPC}}{1 + V_p A}, \quad \nu = \frac{\nu_{FPC} - V_p B}{1 + V_p A} \quad (6)$$

where A and B are the average values of pore contributions (last row of Table 1), porosity V_p and fibre volume fraction V_f can be determined by the analysis of micrograph images (as in Fig. 3), and E_{FPC} , ν_{FPC} are expressed in terms of mechanical properties of the fibres and Pyro-C by Eqn. 4.

Table 1: Hole shape factors of typical Pyro-C pores
(δ_A and δ_B quantify deviation of A and B from average values)

	h_1	h_2	h_3	h_4	h_5	h_6	A	δ_A	B	δ_B
	2.881	5.433	4.875	-1.288	0.479	0.178	4.015	-6.4%	-1.146	0.1%
	2.960	5.042	4.725	-1.210	-0.705	-0.084	3.880	-9.5%	-1.088	-4.9%
	3.628	6.366	5.861	-1.243	-1.186	-1.233	4.902	14.3%	-1.149	0.4%
	6.263	3.399	6.839	-1.104	-0.237	-0.185	5.057	17.9%	-1.330	16.2%
	3.201	6.111	4.804	-1.461	-0.567	-0.353	4.328	0.9%	-1.132	-1.0%
	4.522	3.283	4.792	-1.124	0.607	0.607	3.844	-10.4%	-1.066	-6.9%
	3.025	4.879	5.167	-1.063	-0.164	-0.276	3.990	-6.9%	-1.101	-3.8%
AVERAGE	3.783	4.930	5.295	-1.213	-0.253	-0.192	4.288	0.0%	-1.144	0.0%

EVALUATION OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PYROLYTIC CARBON

Mechanical properties of the pyrolytic carbon in C/C composite strongly depend on the deposition conditions (such as temperature and pressure), and can not be determined from the experiments on the bulk material. We apply the procedure presented in the preceding sections to determine the elastic moduli of the *in-situ* Pyro-C matrix from the tests performed on the entire composite. A series of uniaxial tension, as well as 3- and 4-point bending tests were conducted with the C/C composite specimens, and the elastic moduli of the material were found to be $E_l = 53.6 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_l = 0.33$, $E_t = 4.4 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu_t = 0.29$, where subscripts “*l*” and “*t*” refer to the longitudinal and transverse directions, correspondingly. The mechanical properties of the fibres are known from [4] and [8] as $E_{f,l} = 190 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{f,l} = 0.26$, $E_{f,t} = 14.7 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu_{f,t} = 0.47$. The fibre volume fraction and porosity were found previously as $V_f = 0.18$ and $V_p = 0.29$.

In the *longitudinal* direction, the elastic stiffness of a unidirectional composite can be estimated with a reasonable accuracy by the rule of mixtures. The Young's modulus of the Pyro-C in this direction is then found as

$$E_{PC,l} = \frac{E_l - V_f \cdot E_{f,l}}{1 - V_p - V_f} = \frac{53.6 - 0.18 \cdot 190}{1 - 0.29 - 0.18} = 36.6 \text{ GPa} \quad (7)$$

This value is in a reasonably good agreement with the experimental measurements $E_{PC,l} = 38.6 \text{ GPa}$ of Papadakis and Bernstein [9]. One must remember, however, that the properties of the pyrolytic carbon vary considerably with the change of the manufacturing parameters, so the closeness of our estimates with their ultrasonic measurements might be accidental.

In the *transverse* direction, the procedure is considerably more complicated. It is based on the results of the previous section and follows the steps presented in Fig. 2. First, we have to determine the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the equivalent matrix (FPC) consisting of Pyro-C and carbon fibres. Using Eqn. 6 and the average pore characteristics (Table 1) we obtain $E_{FPC} = 9.7 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu_{FPC} = 0.21$. Then, the transverse properties of Pyro-C are calculated from Eqn. 4 as $E_{PC,t} = 8.6 \text{ GPa}$ and $\nu_{PC,t} = 0.13$.

As can be seen, the elastic stiffnesses of Pyro-C in the longitudinal and transverse directions differ considerably. This can be expected, as the presence of fibres during CVI densification creates preferential directions in pyrolytic carbon – an observation also supported by microscopic studies [1].

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed micromechanical modeling procedure for unidirectional composites involves calculation of the 4-th rank compliance contribution tensors for fibres and pores. For circular elastic fibres, the components of **H**-tensor can be obtained in closed form, and this yields the explicit representations for elastic moduli of the fibre reinforced matrix material. The irregular shapes of pores are analyzed using numerical conformal mapping procedure, and the hole shape factors produced by numerical analysis enter the expressions for the effective elastic constants of the considered composite.

It has been observed that numerical parameters describing the contribution of various pyrolytic carbon pores are relatively close. We attribute this phenomenon to the identical manufacturing procedure during which they were formed. The corresponding parameters of selected regular holes are noticeably different. Thus, there is no obvious way to approximate the real pores in the composite by regular shapes without considerable loss of accuracy.

The CVI densification of the unidirectional C/C composite results in the formation of pyrolytic carbon that has different mechanical properties in the longitudinal and transverse directions. Thus, not only the resulting composite, but also the Pyro-C matrix can not be modeled as isotropic material.

Note that application of the two-step homogenization procedure presented in this paper is not limited to unidirectional composites. It can also be used for micromechanical modeling of random felt C/C composite materials which are also characterized by porosity of different length scale as compare to fibre diameter.

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REFERENCES

1. B. Reznik, D. Gerthsen, and K.J. Hütinger, ”Micro- and nanostructure of the carbon matrix of infiltrated carbon fibre felts”, *Carbon*, Vol. 39(2), 2001, pp. 215-229.
2. I. Tsukrov, R. Piat, J. Novak, and E. Schnack, “Micromechanical Modeling of Porous Carbon/Carbon Composites”, *Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures*, Vol. 12, 2005, pp. 43-54.
3. I. Tsukrov, and J. Novak, “Effective elastic properties of solids with defects of irregular shapes”, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 39, 2002, pp. 1539-1555.
4. R.Ermel., T.Beck, and O.Voehringer, *Carbon from the gas phase: elementary reaction, structures, materials*, Report SFB 551, Karlsruhe University, 2003, pp.353-398.
5. M. Kachanov, I. Tsukrov, and B. Shafiro, “Effective properties of solids with cavities of various shapes”, *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, Vol. 47(1), 1994, pp. S151-S174.
6. O. Eroshkin and I. Tsukrov, “On micromechanical modeling of particulate composites with inclusions of various shapes, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 42, No. 2, 2005, pp. 409-427.
7. N.J. Hardiman, “Elliptic elastic inclusion in an infinite elastic plate”, *Q. J. Mech. Appl. Math*, vol. 7(2), 1954, pp. 226-230.
8. J.B. Donnet, T.K. Wang, S. Rebouillat, and J.C.M. Peng, *Carbon Fibers*, Marcel Dekker, 1998.
9. E.P. Papadakis, and H. Bernstein, “Elastic moduli of pyrolytic graphite”, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, Vol. 35(4), 1963, pp. 521-524.